

WRIGHTIA TINCTORIA (ROXB.) R.BR. A PLANT CONTAINS PHYTOCHEMICALS SHOWING ANTIVENOM PROPERTY BY EXPLORING ELAPID AND VIPER VENOM NEUTRALIZATION POTENTIAL BASED ON MOLECULAR DOCKING. AN IN SILICO APPROACH.

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ABSTRACT

Snakebite envenomation listed as a neglected tropical disease by World health Organisation (WHO). In the current study, we employed an in silico approach to assess bioactive compounds from *Wrightia tinctoria* (Roxb.) R.Br. as potential antivenom agents using key venom target protein phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X). All the selected bioactive molecules showed very good binding energy than the positive control varespladib (-8.54 kcal/mol) and marimastat (-6.09 kcal/mol) except chlorogenic acid, rutin and tryptanthrin. It was found that the ligand ursolic acid scored more negative binding energy -9.16 kcal/mol, -13.94 kcal/mol towards phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) respectively. The bioavailability score reveals that the selected bioactive molecules have ideal oral bioavailability except rutin and chlorogenic acid.

KEYWORDS: • *Wrightia tinctoria* (Roxb.) R.Br. • Phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) • Metalloproteases (2E3X) • Antivenom, • Elapids, • Viper.

INTRODUCTION

Snakebite envenomation is a major threat in public health which causing severe tissue damage, neurotoxicity, kidney failure and death. World health Organisation (WHO) reported snake bite envenoming as a Neglected tropical disease. Antivenom administration is the only choice of treatment for snakebite envenomation which has limitations in terms of cost, availability and accessibility.^[1] Being the snake venom is a complex protein mixture of different enzymes, it is tough to identify the toxicity profile which creates challenges in timely administration of antivenom.^[2] To complement conventional antivenom therapy, recent investigations focus towards identifying herbal bioactive molecules as potential antidotes due to the lower risk of adverse effects.^[3] Earthen hemisphere is blessed with huge number of medicinal plants. Among them, *Wrightia tinctoria* (Figure.1) is an important medicinal plant used in various systems of indian medicine especially in siddha medicine. This plant is inexpensive, easily available, and have pharmacological significance such as antiviral, anti-inflammatory, cytotoxic, hepatoprotective, wound healing, post coital interceptive, anthelmintic, antinociceptive, antioxidant, antiviral, antifungal, antibacterial, antidandruff and antipsoriatic activity.^[4] Molecular docking is an in silico approach provides information about behavior of small molecules, when it binds with receptor target. The main aim of ligand-protein docking is to identify the predominant binding model(s) and understand the interactions of a ligand with amino acid residues of target.^[5]

Figure 1: *Wrightia tinctoria* Plant.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Proteins/Macromolecules

Atractaspidae (69 species), Elapidae (360 species) and Viperidae (340 species) are considered as medically significant venomous snake. Phospholipase A₂, metalloproteases, Serine

proteases and three finger toxins are identified as four main protein families of elapid and viper venom. Among them, phospholipase A₂ and metalloproteases are the two dominant protein families of elapid and viper venom.^[6] To explore the antivenom property of bioactive molecules, phospholipase A₂ and metalloproteases are considered as ideal target. Three dimensional protein structure of PDB ID 6Q42 and PDB ID 2E3X (Figure.2) corresponding to human pancreatic phospholipase A₂ and Russell's viper venom Metalloproteases are downloaded from PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/>), in .pdb format.

PDB ID:6Q42

PDB ID:2E3X

Figure 2: Protein Structure of 6Q42 and 2E3X.

Lead Molecule

Anandie le Roux *et. al.* reported varespladib and marimastat as potential inhibitors of snake venom phospholipase A₂ and metalloproteases.^[7] So, varespladib and marimastat are considered as positive control (Standard) for Phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and Metalloproteases (2E3X) respectively and the structure of the same is given in Figure 3.

Varespladib

Marimastat

Figure 3: Chemical structures of Varespladib and Marimastat.

Selection of ligands and optimization of the geometry

The plant *Wrightia tinctoria* (Figure.1) contains a large number of chemical constituents like steroids, triterpenoids, saponins, tannins, phenols, flavonoids, glycosides, carbohydrates, alkaloids and polyphenols with pharmacological significance.^[8] Among them, fourteen reported phytochemical constituents are selected as ligands. The three dimensional (3D) structures of the selected ligands are downloaded from the <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/> website in the .SDF format and optimized using the Avogadro version 1.2, with Force Field type MMFF94, and saved in .pdb format.^[9] The two dimensional (2D) structures of selected ligands are given in Figure.4.

Figure 4: 2D structures of selected ligands.

Molecular Docking

AutoDock program (version 4.2) was used to perform molecular docking study. All water molecules, heteroatoms, ligand, co-crystallized solvent and inhibitors are removed from the target protein 6Q42 and 2E3X. Polar hydrogens and partial charges were added to the target 6Q42 and 2E3X using Autodock tools (ADT) version 1.5.6.^[10] The binding site region of target proteins 6Q42 and 2E3X are identified using PRANK Web 4.^[11] Grid box was generated in such a way that covers the entire binding site region using suitable X, Y, Z coordinates and the binding affinity was calculated using AutoDock 4.2. The docking score of selected ligands with the target phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) are listed in Table.1 and Table.2 respectively.

Table 1: Summary of the molecular docking studies of the selected ligands against phospholipase A2 (PDB: 6Q42).

Name	Estimated Free Energy of Binding (Kcal/mol)	Estimated Inhibition Constant (Ki)	Van der waals, Hydrogen bonding and desolvation energy Energy (Kcal/mol)	Total Intermolecular Energy (kcal/mol)
Varespladib (Standard)	-8.54	548.94 nM	-10.24	-11.23
Alpha amyirin	-8.73	396.04 nM	-8.96	-9.03
Beta amyirin	-8.71	412.88 nM	-9.02	-9.01
Beta sitosterol	-8.52	569.85 nM	-10.63	-10.61
Campesterol	-9.01	246.92 nM	-10.79	-10.80
Chlorogenic acid	-7.73	2.17 uM	-7.18	-11.01
Cycloartenone	-8.89	302.60 nM	-10.16	-10.09
Cycloeucalenol	-8.90	301.87 nM	-10.70	-10.68
Desmosterol	-8.69	426.70 nM	-10.18	-10.18
Lupeol	-8.20	968.84 nM	-8.76	-8.80
Oleanolic acid	-9.14	200.80 nM	-5.06	-10.03
Rutin	-5.86	50.29 uM	-10.32	-10.64
Stigmasterol	-9.54	101.81 nM	-11.29	-11.33
Tryptanthrin	-7.65	2.46 uM	-7.57	-7.65
Ursolic acid	-9.16	192.60nM	-5.66	-10.06

Table 2: Summary of the molecular docking studies of the selected ligands against metalloproteases (PDB: 2E3X).

Name	Estimated Free Energy of Binding (Kcal/mol)	Estimated Inhibition Constant (Ki)	Van der waals, Hydrogen bonding and desolvation energy Energy (Kcal/mol)	Total Intermolecular Energy (kcal/mol)
Marimastat (Standard)	-6.09	34.48 uM	-8.45	-9.07
Alpha amyirin	-10.64	15.86 nM	-10.49	-10.94
Beta amyirin	-10.67	15.06 nM	-11.01	-10.97
Beta sitosterol	-10.39	24.41 nM	-12.39	-12.47
Campesterol	-10.20	33.38 nM	-11.91	-11.99
Chlorogenic acid	-9.77	69.49 nM	-7.32	-13.05
Cycloartenone	-10.53	19.21 nM	-11.74	-11.72
Cycloeucalenol	-10.45	21.98 nM	-12.18	-12.24
Desmosterol	-9.93	52.23 nM	-11.42	-11.43
Lupeol	-10.30	28.37 nM	-10.79	-10.89
Oleanolic acid	-13.18	218.45 pM	-9.87	-14.07
Rutin	-6.01	39.30 uM	-9.98	-10.78
Stigmasterol	-10.24	30.94 nM	-12.03	-12.03
Tryptanthrin	-7.55	2.94 uM	-7.55	-7.55
Ursolic acid	-13.94	60.15 pM	-10.07	-14.84

Analysis of ligand interaction with amino acid residues of target phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) done by using PLIP (Protein-Ligand interaction profiler) Web tool.^[12] The summary of ligand interaction with amino acid residues of phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) are listed in Table.3 and Table.4 respectively. The detailed view of interaction of five top scored ligands between phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) are illustrated in Figure.5 and Figure.6.

Table 3: Summary of ligand interaction with amino acid residues of target phospholipase A2 (PDB: 6Q42).

Name	Hydrophobic bonds	Distance (Å)	Hydrogen bonds	Distance (Å)	Salt Bridge	Distance (Å)
Varespladib (Standard)	PHE19B, ASN23B, ASN24B, THR120B	3.19, 3.8, 3.59, 3.07	ASN23A, ASN24A, ASP119B, THR120B, THR120B, THR120B	3.05, 2.29, 3.01, 2.1, 2.39, 2.0	-	-
Alpha amyrin	LEU31B, ASP49B, TYR52B, TYR69B	3.25, 3.35, 3.03, 3.34	ASN50B	1.92	-	-
Beta amyrin	TYR52B, LYS56B, ASP66B, PRO68B, TYR69B	3.15, 3.61, 3.49, 3.9, 3.19	-	-	-	-
Beta sitosterol	LEU31B, TYR52B, LYS56B, PRO68B, TYR69B	3.34, 3.37, 3.74, 3.86, 3.22	SER126A	3.36	-	-
Campesterol	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chlorogenic acid	PHE19B, PHE19B, PHE19B, LEU118A, ASP119A	3.25, 3.32, 3.97, 3.52, 3.34	ARG6B, ASP17B, ASP17B, PHE19B, LYS116A, LYS116A	2.45, 3.48, 2.47, 2.33, 2.34, 1.84	ARG6B, LYS122 A, LYS122 A	4.55, 3.36, 3.59
Cycloartenone	TYR28B, GLN46B, ASP49B, ASP49B, TYR52B, ASP53B, LYS56B, ASN67B,	3.17 , 3.77 3.18, 3.46, 3.92, 3.42, 3.41, 3.85, 3.64	-	-	-	-

	PRO68B					
Cycloeucaleanol	TYR28B, ASP49B, ASP49B, TYR52B, ASN67B, TYR69B, TYR69B, GLN125A,	3.34, 3.26, 3.32, 3.6, 3.35, 3.18, 3.63, 3.39,	GLN125A	3.55	-	-
Desmosterol	TYR28B, LEU31B, ASP49B, TYR52B, TYR52B, ASP53B, PRO68B, TYR69B, TYR69B,	3.39, 3.83, 3.19, 2.95, 3.43, 3.36, 3.46, 3.23, 3.83,	GLN125A	3.29	-	-
Lupeol	TYR52B, LYS56B, ASP66B, ASN67B, TYR69B	3.88, 3.15, 3.98, 3.35, 3.14	ASP49B	2.13	-	-
Oleanolic acid	ARG6B, LYS7B, LEU20B	3.22, 3.97, 3.22	-	-	ARG6B, LYS122 A	3.7, 3.92
Rutin	LEU31B, LEU31B, LEU31B, TYR52B, LYS56B, PRO68B	3.71, 2.97, 3.94, 3.93, 3.19, 3.86	LEU31A, GLY32B, GLY33A, GLY33B, GLY33B, GLY33B, TYR69B, TYR69B, GLN125A,	2.01, 1.99, 2.7, 2.21, 3.65, 2.48, 2.18, 1.7, 1.96	-	-
Stigmasterol	ASN24B, LEU31B, THR120B, THR120B	3.34, 3.47, 3.48, 3.63	GLY26B, LEU118B	1.88, 2.43	-	-
Tryptanthrin	-	-	GLY33A	1.78	-	-
Ursolic acid	TRP3B, ARG6B, PHE19B, LEU20B	3.41, 3.29, 3.43, 3.2	-	-	ARG6B, LYS122 A	3.82, 3.76

Figure 5: 3D images of five top scored ligands with phospholipase A₂ (6Q42).

----- Hydrophobic bond -----Hydrogen bond -----Salt bridge interactions

Table 4: Summary of ligand interaction with amino acid residues of target metalloproteases (PDB: 2E3X).

Name	Hydrophobic bonds	Distance (Å)	Hydrogen bonds	Distance (Å)	Salt Bridge	Distance (Å)
Marimastat (Standard)	LEU173A	3.46	LEU108A, LEU111A, LEU111A, GLY112A, HIS155A, PRO171A, LEU173A	2.07, 3.11, 3.29, 2.11, 1.91, 2.24, 3.14	-	-
Alpha amyryin	ASP96A, PHE202A, ASN203A, ARG275A, LEU296A, LEU296A, ASN312A	3.73, 3.38, 3.9, 3.24, 3.36, 3.34, 3.04	ASN203A	2.11	-	-
Beta amyryin	MET90A, ARG293A, ASP294A, ASN312A	3.55, 3.82, 2.84, 3.52	ASP294A	2.27	-	-
Betasitosterol	ASP294A, LEU296A, LEU296A	3.58, 3.02, 3.27	HIS95A, HIS95A, HIS95A	2.23, 2.4, 2.08	-	-
Campesterol	ILE113A, ILE113A, VAL141A, ILE142A, ILE142A, HIS145A, LEU173A, MET390A	3.17, 3.25, 3.79, 3.72, 3.4, 3.62, 3.23, 3.84	MET390A	1.96	-	-
Chlorogenic acid	LYS199A	3.12	CYS120A, ASN203A, ASP294A, ASP294A, ASP314A	2.81, 2.2, 1.96, 1.97, 3.5	LYS199A, ARG275A	4.77, 2.59
Cycloartenone	ASN109A, THR110A, LEU111A, LEU111A, ILE113A, THR114A, HIS149A, VAL172A, LEU173A	3.84, 3.68, 3.83, 3.28, 3.36, 3.78, 3.65, 3.78, 3.35	-	-	-	-
Cycloecalenol	THR110A, LEU	3.86, 3.81,	THR114A	1.83	-	-

	111A, LEU111A, LEU111A, ILE142A, HIS145A, LEU173A, LEU173A	3.49, 3.84, 3.33, 3.53, 3.14, 3.59				
Desmosterol	TYR311A, TYR311A	3.11, 3.25	PRO399A	2.49	-	-
Lupeol	LYS10A, LYS10A, PHE12A, PHE202A, PHE202A, PRO204A, TRP221A, TRP221A, LEU257A, LEU257A, GLU290A	3.02, 3.66, 3.01, 3.81, 2.99, 3.26, 3.78, 3.51, 2.78, 3.49, 2.9	GLU290A, CYS291A, CYS291A	3.56, 2.14, 2.23	-	-
Oleanolic acid	ILE142A, VAL172A, LEU173A	3.18, 3.23, 3.85	ASN109A, PRO171A	2.36, 1.97	HIS145 A, HIS155 A	4.72, 3.74
Rutin	-	-	CYS120A, CYS120A, CYS120A, CYS120A, GLN121A, SER125A, LYS199A, LYS199A, CYS200A, ARG293A, ASN312A, ASP314A, ASP314A	2.29, 2.27, 1.7, 2.08, 3.09, 2.95, 1.84, 3.26, 2.57, 3.42, 2.69, 3.34, 2.51	-	-
Stigmasterol	ASN9A, LYS10A, LYS10A, PHE12A, PHE12A, PHE202A, PRO204A, PRO204A, PRO204A, ILE210A, ILE220A, TRP221A, TRP221A,	3.63, 3.48, 3.6, 3.54, 4, 3.71, 3.06, 3.12, 3.47, 3.35, 3.17, 3.4, 3.18, 3.62, 3.9	ASN9A	2.1	-	-

	ASN255A, LEU257A					
Tryptanthrin	PRO204A, TRP221A, ASN255A, GLU290A	3.75, 3.25, 3.18, 3.33	TRP221A, LEU257A, GLU290A	2.81, 2.77, 2.53	-	-
Ursolic acid	ILE57A, ASN203A, PRO205A, ASP209A	3.17, 3.55, 3.37, 3.03	LYS199A, ASP209A	1.99, 2.53	ARG293 A	3.68

Marimastat (Standard)

Beta amyryn

Cycloartenone

Cycloeucaleanol

Figure.6: 3D images of five top scored ligands with metalloproteases (2E3X).

----- Hydrophobic bond -----Hydrogen bond -----Salt bridge interactions

Drug - likeness and Bioavailability score of selected Ligands

Drug - likeness assessment is very important due to the fact that many herbal drugs are administered via the oral route. Lipinski's rule of five clearly provides information about the oral bioavailability of the drug using physiochemical parameters like molecular weight (≤ 500), number of hydrogen bond donors (≤ 5), octanol/water partition coefficient ($\text{LogP} \leq 5$) and number of hydrogen bond acceptors (≤ 10).^[13] Based on this rule, for a drug molecule to be orally bioavailable, it must not violate more than one of aforesaid parameters. The number of violation of Lipinski's rule and oral bioavailability (BA) score were predicted using SWISS ADME online tool and the results are given in the table.5.^[14]

Table 5: Bioavailability (BA) scores of selected ligands.

Name	Number of violation on Lipinski rule of five	Fraction Csp3	MW (g/mol)	TPSA (Å ²)	XLOGP3	Number of Rotatable bonds	BA score
Varespladib (Standard)	0	0.19	380.39	111.62	2.75	8	0.56
Marimastat (Standard)	0	0.80	331.41	127.76	0.51	11	0.55
Alpha amyirin	1	0.93	426.72	20.23	9.01	0	0.55
Beta amyirin	1	0.93	426.72	20.23	9.15	0	0.55
Beta sitosterol	1	0.93	414.71	20.23	9.34	6	0.55
Campesterol	1	0.93	400.68	20.23	8.80	5	0.55
Chlorogenic acid	1	0.38	354.31	164.75	-0.42	5	0.11
Cycloartenone	1	0.90	424.70	17.07	9.46	4	0.55
Cycloeucalenol	1	0.93	426.72	20.23	9.91	5	0.55
Desmosterol	1	0.85	384.64	20.23	8.27	4	0.55
Lupeol	1	0.93	426.72	20.23	9.87	1	0.55
Oleanolic acid	1	0.90	456.70	57.53	7.49	1	0.85
Rutin	3	0.44	610.52	269.43	-0.33	6	0.17
Stigmasterol	1	0.86	412.69	20.23	8.56	5	0.55
Tryptanthrin	0	0.00	248.24	51.96	2.05	0	0.55
Ursolic acid	1	0.90	456.70	57.53	7.34	1	0.85

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the outcome of docking analysis, out of fourteen selected bioactive compounds, except rutin, all the compounds showed very good binding energy towards the target protein phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X). Except chlorogenic acid, rutin and tryptanthrin, all other ligands showed about similar and more negative binding energy towards the target phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) than the positive control varespladib (-8.54 kcal/mol). In case of the target metalloproteases (2E3X), other than rutin, all the selected ligands showed more negative binding energy than the positive control marimastat (-6.09 kcal/mol). The aforesaid results clearly indicate that most of the selected ligands form strong and stable complex with the target protein phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X). The ligand ursolic acid scored more negative binding energy -9.16 kcal/mol, -13.94 kcal/mol towards phospholipase A₂ (6Q42) and metalloproteases (2E3X) respectively. Moreover, The bioavailability score of selected ligand clearly reveals that, all the ligands have ideal oral bioavailability based on theoretical foundation except rutin and chlorogenic acid. The ligand ursolic acid and oleanolic acid showed higher bioavailability score of 0.85 than the positive control varespladib (0.56) and marimastat (0.55).

CONCLUSION

This study employed an *in silico* approach to assess bioactive compounds from *Wrightia tinctoria* (Roxb.) R.Br. as potential antivenom agents. To our best knowledge, we are reporting first the antivenom potential of bioactive compounds from this species using molecular docking analysis. The results suggest that the plant *Wrightia tinctoria* (Roxb.) R.Br. have many bioactive molecules with antivenom potential based on molecular docking. The Phytoconstituent ursolic acid is predicted to exhibit stable and high affinity interaction with key venom proteins. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluations are required to confirm the therapeutic efficacy. The outcome of the present study will provide new opportunities to allopathic and other alternative system of medicines for creating innovative treatments of venomous bites.

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